

Studies in Acenaphthenone. Part I. Pirylium Derivatives.

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Decker and Fellenberg (*Ber.*, 1907, **40**, 3815; *Annalen*, 1907, **356**, 281), Perkin, Robinson and Turner (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, **93**, 1085), Pratt and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **121**, 1577; *ibid.*, 1923, **123**, 743 etc.), De (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **4**, 23, 137) and others have shown that *o*-hydroxyaldehydes can condense with substances containing the group-CH₂-CO-under certain conditions to form pyrylium compounds. It was therefore natural to expect that acenaphthenone which also contains the group-CH₂-CO-would yield pyrylium derivatives. This expectation has been amply rewarded by the preparation of pyrylium derivatives by the condensation of acenaphthenone with salicylic and β -resorecylic aldehydes. Condensations were effected in two different ways, *viz.*, (1) by passing gaseous hydrogen chloride through a glacial acetic acid solution of equimolecular quantities of the respective aldehydes and acenaphthenone (Decker and Fellenberg, *loc. cit.*),

(2) by first preparing the *o*-hydroxystyryl ketone by condensation of the aldehyde and acenaphthenone in alkaline solution and subsequently converting it into the pyrylium salt by the action of dry gaseous hydrogen chloride (Pratt and Robinson, *loc. cit.*).

In the case of salicylic aldehyde, the free pyrylium chloride could not be isolated, as it decomposed immediately in contact with air. The corresponding ferri-chlorides and the perchlorates are, however, quite stable and were obtained in beautiful crystalline forms. In the

case of β -resorcylic aldehyde, in addition to the ferri-chloride and the perchlorate the free pyrylium chloride, which is quite stable, were also obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL.

2:3-Acenaphthbenzopyrylium Chloride.

Acenaphthenone (0.5 g.) and salicylic aldehyde (0.38 g.) were dissolved in glacial acetic acid (10 c.c.) and dry hydrochloric gas was passed through the solution for $1\frac{1}{2}$ —2 hours. The almost colourless solution gradually turned yellow and finally became orange yellow. The completion of the reaction was indicated when there was no further precipitation on the addition of a little of the reaction mixture to dilute hydrochloric acid. The solution was then poured into a large volume of ether and the yellow solid pyrylium chloride separated after some time. The ethereal layer was decanted off and the solid, after being quickly filtered and washed with ether, was kept in a vacuum desiccator. So long as the substance was in the desiccator it was solid, but on removal immediate decomposition set in with the liberation of hydrogen chloride gas and the solid became resinous. The solid is so unstable in air that it was not possible even to take the melting point. The solid is soluble in dilute hydrochloric acid (1:1) and glacial acetic acid. It is sparingly soluble in alcohol and insoluble in all other organic solvents.

2:3-Acenaphthbenzopyrylium ferri-chloride. — It was obtained as a dark yellow precipitate by adding ferric chloride, dissolved in concentrated hydrochloric acid into the glacial acetic acid solution of the pyrylium chloride described in the previous experiment. The addition of ferric chloride was continued until the precipitation was complete. It was then filtered and washed with moderately dilute hydrochloric acid, and finally with alcohol. It was obtained as yellow shining rectangular plates from boiling acetic acid. The crystals were dried over potash in a desiccator, m.p. 208° . It gives a straw yellow coloration with concentrated sulphuric acid from which it is not precipitated back on dilution. It decomposes when dissolved in water. It is insoluble in all organic solvents excepting acetic acid.

(Found: C, 51.04; H, 2.39. $C_{19}H_{11}O$, $FeCl_4$ requires C, 50.86; H, 2.43 per cent.).

2:3-Acenaphthbenzopyrylium perchlorate.—To the solution of 2:3-acenaphthbenzopyrylium chloride in glacial acetic acid, perchloric acid was added drop by drop until the separation of the crystals was complete. The separated shining yellow plates were filtered, washed first with glacial acetic acid and then with ether, and finally dried in the desiccator over potash. It melts at 255° with decomposition, and decomposes in presence of water. It gives a greenish yellow colour with concentrated sulphuric acid. (Found: C, 63.98; H, 3.50. $C_{19}H_{12}O_5Cl$ requires C, 64.13, H, 3.31 per cent.).

2:3-Acenaphthbenzopyrylium chloride. Second method).

(a) *Salicylidene acenaphthenone*.—Acenaphthenone (0.5 g.) and salicylic aldehyde (0.38 g.) were dissolved in the least quantity of alcohol and alcoholic potash (about 5 c.c. of 10 p.c.) added. The scarlet red solution obtained did not separate any precipitate even on standing. The solution was then poured into ether when a scarlet-red slimy precipitate was obtained which stuck to the sides of the vessel. The supernatant liquid was poured away and dilute hydrochloric acid added to the precipitate, when the colour changed to yellow. It was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from dilute alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 186° .

(b) *Conversion of salicylidene acenaphthenone to the corresponding pyrylium chloride and the ferri-chloride*.—Salicylidene acenaphthenone (0.4 g.) was suspended in dry ether and dry hydrogen chloride gas passed through the suspension for about two hours. The solution gradually turned deep yellow and finally orange yellow. The pale yellow needles which were at the bottom gradually disappeared, and a dirty yellow amorphous powder separated. The completion of the reaction was indicated by the complete solubility of a sample in dilute hydrochloric acid after removal of ether. After the reaction was over, dilute hydrochloric acid was added to the mixture and ether distilled off. Care was taken to see that the concentration of the acid was sufficient to prevent hydrolysis of the oxonium salt. (1:1 HCl used). The solution was filtered and to the filtrate ferric chloride in concentrated hydrochloric acid added as in the previous preparation. The separated ferri-chloride was found to be identical with the one obtained previously.

7-Hydroxy-2:3-acenaphthbenzopyrylium chloride.—Acenaphthenone (1.5 g.) and β -resorcylic aldehyde (0.4 g.) were dissolved in

glacial acetic acid (8 c.c.) and dry hydrogen chloride gas passed through the solution. Reaction soon began as indicated by the change of the colour of the solution to deep red. On passing hydrogen chloride for about three hours deep red needles filled the whole liquid. The mixture was poured into a large excess of ether when whole of the solid got precipitated. This was filtered and washed with ether. The precipitate was then dissolved in hot dilute hydrochloric acid (1:1) and filtered hot to free it from any unreacted acenaphthenone. The filtrate, on cooling, deposited beautiful scarlet red needles, which were filtered and dried in a vacuum desiccator over potash. It melts at 131°. It is insoluble in almost all organic solvents but sparingly soluble in acetic acid. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid giving an orange solution with a greenish fluorescence and is not precipitated back on dilution. It decomposes in contact with water and also when kept in moist air for a long time. (Found: C, 73.99; H, 3.85. $C_{19}H_{11}O_2Cl$ requires, C, 74.39; H, 3.58 per cent.).

The same compound was obtained by passing hydrogen chloride gas through a suspension of β -resorcyldeneacenaphthenone in dry ether. The experiment was conducted exactly in the same way as in the case of the corresponding salicylidene compound—only the hydrogen chloride gas was passed for a longer time (3 hours). The pyrylium chloride was purified as in the preceding case.

7-Hydroxy-2:3-acenaphthbenzopyrylium ferri-chloride.—It was prepared from the preceding compound in the same way as the corresponding ferri-chloride from 2:3-acenaphthbenzopyrylium chloride. The separated solid was purified by dissolving in a large excess of boiling acetic acid. On cooling, chocolate coloured needles separated. These were filtered, washed with ether, and dried. It decomposes at 236-37°. It is insoluble in almost all other organic solvents. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid imparting to it a brownish colour with greenish fluorescence. (Found: C, 48.73; H, 2.44. $C_{19}H_{11}O_2$, $FeCl_4$ requires C, 48.64; H, 2.34 per cent.).

7-Hydroxy-2:3-Acenaphthbenzopyrylium perchlorate.—It was prepared and purified in a similar way and possessed properties similar to 2:3-acenaphthbenzopyrylium perchlorate (*vide supra*). It melts at 260° (decomp.) and burns with explosion. (Found: C, 61.27; H, 3.40. $C_{19}H_{12}O_4Cl$ requires C, 61.37; H, 3.23 per cent.).